

GREEK PAPYRI AT THE MUSEUM OF NEW ZEALAND TE PAPA TONGAREWA, WELLINGTON

1. Te Papa GH023780.
Homer, *Odyssey* 6.264-275, 6.294-305

- = P. Oxy. 11 1395, ed. Grenfell, Bernard P.; Hunt, Arthur S.
- = Trismegistos TM 61004
- = (formerly) Wellington Dominion Museum G. 1668

Title: Papyrus, 'Homer, Odyssey vi'

Dimensions: 64 mm (H) × 77 mm (W)

Date: 301-400 CE

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Society to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1922; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri* 11 (1915):

'1395. 6.5 × 8.9 cm. Fragment of a vellum leaf containing on one side the first halves of ζ 264-75 and on the other 294-305, with frequent accents and marks of elision added in lighter ink. Stops in the high position occur. 269 σπειρας, the final c rewritten and repeated in lighter ink above the line. 273 φ of φημιν corrected; a paragraphus was inserted by a later hand

below this line. 274 ι adscript of μωμευηι· added together with a high stop by a later hand. εἰσὶν. 297 ἐλθ]ης corrected to ἐλθ]ηι by a later hand. 303 κευθωσι. Fourth century; in a fine upright script rather similar to that of the Codex Sinaiticus.’

Further notes (PG):

Sheet from a vellum (not papyrus) codex, 30 lines per side. Homer, *Odyssey* 6.264-275 (recto) and 6.294-305 (verso).

This papyrus has one distinctive textual reading, 303 κεύθωσι; the majority of mediaeval manuscripts read κεκύθωσι, or less often, κεκεύθωσι.

For line 297, the description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri* erroneously reads ‘ἐλθ]ης corrected to ἐλθ]ηι by a later hand’: it should read ‘ἐλπ]ης corrected to ἐλπ]ηι by a later hand’.

References:

The Oxyrhynchus Papyri 11 (1915): p. 244 ([Oxyrhynchus Online link](#))

Trismegistos: <http://www.trismegistos.org/tm/detail.php?tm=61004>

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347756>

Bibliography:

Garvie, A. F. 1994. *Homer. Odyssey books VI-VIII*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. p. 156.

Text, recto:

- [... λεπτή δ' εἰσίθ]μη· νῆες [δ' ὁδὸν ἀμφιέλιςσαι]
 265 [εἰρύαται·] πᾶσιν γὰρ ἐπίστ[ιὸν ἐστὶν ἐκάστῳ].
 [ἔν]θα δέ τέ σφ' ἀγορὴ καλὸ[ν Ποσιδήϊον ἀμφίς],
 ῥυτοῖσιν λάεσσι κατωρυ[χέεσσ' ἀραρυῖα].
 ἔνθα δὲ νηῶν ὄπλα μελ[αινάων ἀλέγουσι],
 πείσματα καὶ σπείρας, καὶ [ἀποξύνουσιν ἐρετμά].
 270 [οὐ γ]ὰρ Φαιήκεσσι μέλει β[ιὸς οὐδὲ φαρέτρῃ],
 [ἀλλ'] ἴστοι καὶ ἐρετμὰ νεῶν [καὶ νῆες εἴσαι],
 ἦσι[ι]ν ἀγαλλόμενοι πολ[ιὴν περώσιν θάλασσαν].
 τῶ[ν ἀ]λεείνω φῆμιν ἀδε[υκέα, μή τις ὀπίσσω]
 μωμεύη ἰ· μάλα δ' εἰσὶν ὑπε[ρφίαλοι κατὰ δῆμον].
 275 [κα]ί νύ τις ᾧδ' εἴπησι κακῶ[τερος ἀντιβολήσας].

269 σπείρας: -[[c]]`c' 273 φῆμιν: [[φ]]`φ'-

Text, verso:

- [τόσσον ἀπὸ πτόλιος, ὅσσο]ν [τε γέγωνε βοήσας].
 295 [ἔνθα καθεζόμενος μεῖναι χρόνον, [εἰς ὃ κεν ἡμεῖς]
 [ἄστυδε ἔλθωμεν καὶ ἰκ]ώμεθα δώματα πα[τρός].
 [αὐτὰρ ἐπὴν ἡμεας ἔλπ]ηι ποτὶ δώματ' ἀφῖχθαι,
 [καὶ τότε Φαιήκων ἴμε]ν ἐς πόλιν ἠδ' ἐρέεσθαι
 [δώματα πατρὸς ἐμοῦ] μεγαλήτορος Ἀλκινόοιο.
 300 [ρεῖα δ' ἀρίγνωτ' ἐστί, καὶ] ἂν πάϊς ἠγήσαιο
 [νήπιος· οὐ μὲν γὰρ τι] εἰκότα τοῖσι τέτυκται
 [δώματα Φαιήκων, ο]ἶος δόμος Ἀλκινόοι[ο]
 [ἦρωσ. ἀλλ' ὀπὸτ' ἂν σε δ]όμοι κεύθωσι καὶ αὐ[λή],
 [ᾧκα μάλα μεγάροι]ο διελθέμεν, ὄφρ' ἂν ἴκηαι
 305 [μητέρ' ἐμήν· ἠ δ' ἦσ]ται ἐπ' ἐσχάρηι ἐν πυρὸς [αὐγῆι],

297 ἔλπ]ηι: m¹ ἔλπ]ης, m² -[[c]]`ι' 303 κεύθωσι: cett. κεκύθωσι, nonnulli κεκεύθωσι

Translation (Gainsford):

(*Nausikaa is speaking to Odysseus*) ... ²⁶⁴ (the harbour has) [an easy entran]ce; [and along the road curved] ships ²⁶⁵ [are drawn up]; for there is a slipway on all of them, [on each one]. And their agora is [th]ere, [around] a fine [temple of Poseidon, decorated] with stones quarried and dug [out]. And there [they care for] their da[rk] ships' equipment, the cables and ropes, and [they whittle the oars]. ²⁷⁰ For the Phaiakes do not care for the b[ow or quiver, but] masts and ships' oars, [and balanced ships], in wh[i]ch they delight [in crossing the] grey [sea]. I would [a]void having a cru[el] reputation among the[m, in case in future] they should criticise me: there are some ver[y arrogant ones among the people]. ²⁷⁵ [An]d then some infer[ior person] would say this, [if he met me]: ... (*eighteen lines missing*) ²⁹⁴ (My father's estate is) [as far away from the city a]s [someone can make their shout carry. ²⁹⁵ Sit down there and w]ait a while, [until we can

get to the city and ar]rive at the house of my fa[ther. But when you thi]nk [we] have arrived at home, [then g]o into the city [of the Phaiakes] and ask [for the house of my father], great-hearted Alkinoos. ³⁰⁰[It is easily recognisable, and] perhaps a child will guide you, [a little one. For] the Phaiakes' houses are built [not at all] like it, [l]ike the home of Alkinoo[s the hero. But when the h]ome has concealed [you], and the courty[ard], go [very quickly] through [the hal]l until you get to ³⁰⁵[my mother; she si]ts by the hearth in the fire[light] ...

**2. Te Papa GH023781.
Customs receipt from the Small Oasis**

- = P. Oxy. 12 1439, ed. Grenfell, Bernard P.; Hunt, Arthur S.
- = *Select Papyri* 2 381, ed. Hunt, Arthur S.; Edgar, Campbell Cowan
- = Trismegistos TM 21842
- = (formerly) Wellington Dominion Museum G. 1669

Title: Papyrus, 'Customs Receipt'

Dimensions: 53 mm (H) × 51 mm (W)

Date: 1 February 70 CE

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Society to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1922; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*:

‘1439. Customs-Receipt.

‘5.3 × 5.3 cm. A.D. 75.

‘This is the first example from Oxyrhynchus of a class of tax-receipts which is common in Arsinoïte papyri, concerning octroi-dues levied upon traffic across the western desert; cf. P. Fay. pp. 195 sqq., Wilcken, *Ost.* i. 354 sqq. and *Archiv.* ii. 134, P. Ryl. 197 int. The general character of the formula resembles that of the other first and early second century instances, in which πάρεσχε or παρήξει is used in place of the later τετελώνηται, e.g. P. Brit. Mus. 1265; but it is noteworthy that the tax is only 1/100 and is called διαπυλίο(υ), a word which here appears for the first time in a papyrus, whereas the Arsinoïte receipts mention two taxes, of 1/100 and 1/50, which are not further specified, διὰ πύλης with the name of a village occurring immediately after the verb. In the present case produce was being transported probably from the Small Oasis (where the tax was paid) to Oxyrhynchus rather than vice versa. The Small Oasis was united to the Oxyrhynchite nome for some purposes in the later Roman period; cf. [P. Oxy.] 888. 8 (about A. D. 300) ἐξηγητῆ Ὀξυρυγ[χίτου κ]αὶ Μικρᾶς Ὀάσεως, [P. Oxy.] 485 (A. D. 178), where an inhabitant of the Oasis came under the jurisdiction of the Oxyrhynchite strategus. In other cases the Oasis was more distinct; cf. [P. Oxy.] 1118. 1 (about A. D. 100), which mentions the strategus of the Small Oasis, [P. Oxy.] 1498. 6 (before 299) στρα(τηγία) Ὀάσεως (sc. Μικρᾶς?), and [P. Oxy.] 1210. 16 (about A. D. 1), where the [κω]μογρα[μματεῖ]ς Ὀάσεως τῆς πρὸς τῶι [Ὀξυρυγχίτη? are distinguished from the κωμογρ. Ὀξυρυγχίτου. The absence of the usual πεντηκοστή ἐξαγωγῆς or εἰσαγωγῆς (cf. [P. Oxy.] 1440) may be due to the circumstance that none was levied upon traffic between the Oasis and the nome, and in any case a contrast is to be drawn between the ἑκατοστὴ διαπυλίου, which was levied at πύλαι in the villages bordering on the desert, and the πεντηκοστή on exports and imports, which was levied on traffic by water as well as land, and outside the Arsinoïte nome was collected separately, so far as is known; cf. [P. Oxy.] 1440. int.

‘The writing is across the fibres, and, as usual, there is a seal, which is undecipherable.’

Further notes (PG): *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*, and the Loeb edition of *Select Papyri*, give the date of the papyrus as 75 CE, but lines 3-5 put the papyrus in the second year of Vespasian’s reign, that is, 70 CE. See Sijpesteijn 1987: 102.

The Small Oasis = modern Bahariya (28.4° N, 28.9° E), ca. 170 km west of Oxyrhynchus.

References

The Oxyrhynchus Papyri 12 (1916): pp. 112-113 ([Oxyrhynchus Online link](#))

Trismegistos: <http://www.trismegistos.org/text/21842>

Papyri.info: <http://papyri.info/ddbdp/p.oxy;12;1439>

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347879>

Loeb Classical Library: *Select Papyri. Official Documents. Receipts* (1934) pp. 484-485 ([LCL online link](#); [Internet Archive link](#))

Bibliography:

Calderini, A.; Daris, S. 1982. *Dizionario dei nomi geografici e topografici dell’Egitto greco-romano* III. Milan. p. 379.

Jouguet, P.; Guéraud, O. 1933. ‘Ostraca grecs d’Eléphantine.’ *Aegyptus* 13.3-4: 443-454, at p. 447.

- Maitingly, D. J., et al. (eds.) 2017. *Trade in the ancient Sahara and beyond*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. p. 270.
- Parker, Floyd O. 2001. ““Our Lord and God” in Rev 4,11: evidence for the late date of Revelation?” *Biblica* 82.2: 207-231, at p. 216.
- Reiter, Fabian. 2004. *Die Nomarchen des Arsinoites. Ein Beitrag zum Steuerwesen im römischen Ägypten*. Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh. p. 248.
- Sijpesteijn, P. J. 1987. *Customs duties in Graeco-Roman Egypt*. Zutphen: Terra. p. 102.
- Wagner, Guy 1987. *Les oasis d'Égypte à l'époque grecque, romaine et byzantine d'après les documents grecs: recherches de papyrologie et d'épigraphie grecques*. Cairo: Institut français d'archéologie orientale du Caire. pp. 147, 289.

Text, recto:

παρέ(σχηκε) Σαραπίων (έκατοστήν) διαπυλίο<υ>

Ἰάσ(εως) κριθῆς ὄνον ἕνα καὶ

σκόρδων ὄνον ἕνα. (ἔτους) β(')

Οὐεσπασιανοῦ τοῦ κυρίου

5 Μ[ε]χεῖρ ἑβδόμη ζ(').

Translation (Gainsford):

Sarapion has paid (the 1% tax) for Oasis customs dues upon one ass-load of barley and one ass-load of garlic. (Year) 2 of the lord Vespasian, Mecheir the seventh (day), 7.

3. Te Papa GH023782. Surety declaration

= P. Oxy. 12 1554, ed. Grenfell, Bernard P.; Hunt, Arthur S.

= Trismegistos TM 21920

= (formerly) Wellington Dominion Museum G. 1670

Title: Papyrus, 'Declaration of Surety for a Ship Owner'

Dimensions: 132 mm (H) × 80 mm (W)

Date: 4 December 251 CE

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Society to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1922; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*:

'1554. 13.7 × 8.3 cm. A. D. 251. Conclusion of a declaration on oath for surety of a boat-owner, addressed to a strategus (cf. l. 8 with [P. Oxy.] 1555. 14), similar to [P. Oxy.] 1555; cf. also [P. Oxy.] 1553.'

Further notes (PG):

This papyrus, dated to the 7th day of Choiak (4 December), is our earliest Egyptian evidence for the recognition of Volusian as Roman emperor (r. 251-253 CE). Volusian had become co-emperor with his father Trebonianus Gallus only a month or so earlier, upon the death of the previous co-emperor Hostilian.

Line 7 *καφοπάκτων* is a hapax legomenon. Grenfell and Hunt note, 'for *πάκτων* cf. Reil, *Beiträge*, 88.'

Sesphtha probably = modern Sumusta (28.914° N, 30.853° E), 47 km NNE of Oxyrhynchus.

The

References:

The Oxyrhynchus Papyri 12 (1916): p. 273

Trismegistos: <http://www.trismegistos.org/tm/detail.php?tm=21920>

Papyri.info: <http://papyri.info/ddbdp/p.oxy;12;1554>

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347897>

Bibliography:

Packman, Z. M. 1991. 'Notes on papyrus texts with the Roman imperial oath.' *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik* 89: 91-102. p. 96.

Rathbone, D. W. 1986. 'The dates of the recognition in Egypt of the emperors from Caracalla to Diocletianus.' *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik* 62: 101-131.

Strobel, Karl 1993. *Das Imperium Romanum im '3. Jahrhundert'. Modell einer historischen Krise?* Stuttgart: Franz Steiner. p. 231.

Text, recto:

lines missing

0a [. . . ὀμνύω τὴν τῶν]

0b [κυρίων Γαίου Οὐιβίου Τρεβωνι]-

0c [ανοῦ Γάλλου καὶ Γαίου Οὐιβίου]

1 [Α]φινί[ου Γάλλου Οὐελδουμνιανοῦ]

Οὐολου[cianoῦ Εὐσεβῶν Εὐτυχῶν]

Σεβαστῶν τῆ[χην ἐκουσίως καὶ αὐθαι-]

ρέτως ἐγγυᾶσθαι Αὐρήλ[ιον Πετόσι-(?)]

5 ριν Ὀννώφριος μητρὸς Τιρότος ἀπὸ

κώμης Σέσφθα κυβερνήτην πλοί-

ου ἰδίου καφοπάκτωνος ἐμφανῆ

ὄντα, ὃν καὶ παραστήσω σοι ὁπόταν
 ἐπιζητηθῆ, ἢ ἐγὼ αὐτὸς ὑφέξομαι
 10 τὸν ὑπὲρ αὐτοῦ λόγον, ἢ ἔνοχος εἶην
 τῷ ὄρκῳ. (ἔτους) β' Αὐτοκρατόρων
 Καϊσάρων Γαίου Οὐιβίου Τρεβ[ωνιανοῦ]
 Γάλλου καὶ Γαίου Οὐιβίου Ἀφ[ινίου]
 Γάλλου Οὐελδουμνιανοῦ Οὐολ[ουσιανοῦ]
 15 Εὐσεβῶν Εὐτυχῶν Σεβαστῶν [μηνὸς]
 Χ[ο]ίακ ζ.
 [Αὐ]ρήλιος Κάσσιος Ἀπολλ[ωνίου]
traces of two lines

0a-0c Packman 4 ἐγγυᾶσθαι: εγ'γ- 7 Σέσφθα: cf. P. Oxy. 1423. 10, n.
 9 ὑφέξομαι: ὑφεξ-

Translation (Gainsford):

[I, ... , swear by the] fortune [of the emperor Caesars, Gaius Vibius Trebonianus Gallus and ¹A]fini[us Gallus Veldumnianus] Volu[sianus, the Pii Felices] Augusti, willingly and voluntarily, that it is pledged that Aurelios Petosiris, ⁵ son of (his father) Onnophris and his mother Tisoīs, from the village of Sesphta, is publicly recognised as helmsman of his own boat, which is a *skaphopaktōn*. I shall pledge this to you whenever an enquiry is made: either I shall personally support ¹⁰ the declaration on his behalf, or I shall be liable for the oath. (Year) 2 of the emperor Caesars Gaius Vibius Trebonianus Gallus and Gaius Vibius Afinius Gallus Veldumnianus Volusianus, the ¹⁵ Pii Felices Augusti, 7th of [the month of] Choiak. Aurelius Cassius Apollonius ...

Title: Papyrus, 'Letter of Harpokration'

Dimensions: 123 mm (H) × 96 mm (W)

Date: ca. 201-225 CE

Author: Harpokration

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Society to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1922; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*:

'1586. 12.5 × 9.5 cm. Early third century. A letter from a man to his 'sister', consisting of the conventional good wishes and salutations. A midwife (ιατρίνη) is mentioned in l. 12.'

Further notes (PG):

Grenfell and Hunt take the word ιατρίνη (line 12) as 'midwife', but the normal word for that is μαῖα. Both words appear elsewhere in the Greco-Roman world, but this is the only Egyptian reference to an ιατρίνη. In itself ιατρίνη implies a woman who is a medical practitioner, so the most natural interpretation is 'female doctor'. (So also Froschauer and Römer 2007: 8; Draycott 2011: 142.)

References:

The Oxyrhynchus Papyri 12 (1916): p. 283 ([Oxyrhynchus Online link](#))

Trismegistos: <http://www.trismegistos.org/tm/detail.php?tm=31768>

Papyri.info: <http://papyri.info/ddbdp/p.oxy;12;1586>

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347906>

Bibliography:

Dickey, Eleanor 2004. 'Rules without reasons? Words for children in papyrus letters.' In: Penney, J. H. W. (ed.) *Indo-European perspectives. Studies in honour of Anna Morpurgo Davies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. pp. 119-130, at p. 124.

Draycott, Jane Louise 2011. *Approaches to healing in Roman Egypt* ([link 1](#), [link 2](#)). Diss. Nottingham. p. 142.

Froschauer, H.; Römer, C. (eds.) 2007. *Zwischen Magie und Wissenschaft: Ärzte und Heilkunst in den Papyri aus Ägypten*. Vienna: Phobos. pp. 8, 17.

Nifosi, A. 2019. *Becoming a woman and mother in Greco-Roman Egypt: women's bodies, society and domestic space*. Abingdon: Routledge. pp. 54-56.

Text, recto:

Ἀρποκρατίων Ἡραΐδι τῆι

ἀδελφῆι χαίρειν.

πρὸ τῶν ὄλων εὐχομαί

σε ὑγιαίνειν μετὰ τῶν τέ-

5 κνων σου καὶ τῶν σῶν πάν-

των. γράφω δέ σοι καὶ ἐγὼ

ἐρρωμένος καὶ εὐχόμενος

σοι τὰ κάλλιστα. ἄσπασαι Ἄ-

πολλώνιον καὶ Διονύσιον καὶ

10 Πλουτογένειαν καὶ Εὐτυχίαν

καὶ τοὺς υἱοὺς αὐτῆς καὶ τὴν θυ-

γατέρα. ἡ ἱατρίνη (ἱατρ-) σε ἀσπάζε-

ται καὶ Διονύσιος καὶ Ἡρων
καὶ οἱ ἐμοὶ πάντες σε προσαγο-
15 ρεύουσιν. ἐρρῶσθ(αι) εὔχομ(αι) [π]ανοικεῖ.

Text, verso:

Αὐρηλία [Ἡραΐδι] π(αρά) ἀδελ(φοῦ) Ἄρποκρατίωνος.

Translation (Gainsford):

Harpokration greets his sister Heraïs. Before all things I pray that you are healthy, along with your children ⁵ and all your family. As I write to you I too am well and praying for all the best for you. Say hello to Apollonios, Dionysios, ¹⁰ Ploutogeneia, and Eutychia, and her sons and daughter. The (female) doctor says to say hello to you, and so do Dionysios and Heron and all my family. ¹⁵ I pray things are well for the whole household.

(reverse)

For Aurelia Heraïs, from her brother Harpokration

5. Te Papa GH023784. Real estate sale

= P. Oxy. 14 1700, ed. Grenfell, Bernard P.; Hunt, Arthur S.

= Trismegistos TM 31792

= (formerly) Wellington Dominion Museum G. 1672

Title: Papyrus, 'Sale of Land and House-property'

Dimensions: 124 mm (H) × 151 mm (W)

Date: ca. 276-300 CE

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Society to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1922; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Description in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*:

'1700. 12.4 × 15.1 cm. Late third century, in the 1st year of an emperor (l. 20). The middle part of a contract for the sale of arable and vine-land, a pigeon-house, and house-property at Seruphis (cf. [P. Oxy.] 1285. 71) for 2 talents.'

Further notes (PG):

Line 8 ἐπερωτηθεῖς, lit. ‘after being questioned’, refers to *stipulatio*, in law the condition of being capable and willing to enter into a contract.

Lines 19-20: the intercalary days or *epagomenai* were the last five days of the year in the Alexandrian calendar (or in leap years, the last six days).

The phrasing of the guarantee of ownership (lines 9-14, κρατεῖν ... καὶ κυριεύειν up to πάση βεβαιώσει) is largely formulaic: cf. adjacent papyri in *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri* 14.

Certain idiosyncratic spellings here are regular in contracts of this kind, notably 10-11 μεταλημφομένοις (‘successors’) with -λημψ- /*lēbs-*/ for -ληψ-, and 16 σειτικά (‘pertaining to grain’) for σιτικά.

Seryphis probably = modern Ashruba (28.515° N, 30.713° E), about 5 km east of Oxyrhynchus.

References:

The Oxyrhynchus Papyri 14 (1920): pp. 155-156 ([Oxyrhynchus Online link](#))

Trismegistos: <http://www.trismegistos.org/tm/detail.php?tm=31792>

Papyri.info: <http://papyri.info/ddbdp/p.oxy;14;1700>

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347922>

Text, recto:

lines missing

- 1 κώμη Σερύφει ... [.....
 5 ον καὶ ὀλόκληρον περιστερεῶνα καὶ οἰκίαν καὶ αὐλήν σὺν χρη-
 στηρίοις καὶ ἀνήκουσι πᾶσι, ὧν ὄλων γείτονες νότου Τασωτ[ᾶ(?)],
 βορρᾶ διῶρυξ, ἀπηλιῶτου δημοσία ρύμη, λιβὸς ἐτέρων φιλοὶ τό-
 10 ποὶ, τὰς δὲ συμπεφωνημένας πρὸς ἀλλήλους ὑπὲρ τιμῆς
 [τ]ῶν προκειμένων πάντων ἀργυρίου Σεβαστοῦ νομίματος
 [δ]ραχμὰς μυριάδαν μίαν διςχειλίας, αἶ εἰς ἀργυρίου τάλαντα
 [δύ]ο, αὐτόθι ἀπ[έ]σχον, καὶ ἐπερωτηθεῖς ὡμολόγησα ἠριθμῆ-
 [σθαι ἐμὲ] παρὰ σοῦ διὰ χειρὸς ἐκ πλήρους. κρατεῖν οὖν σε
 15 καὶ κυριεύειν σὺν ἐγγόνοις καὶ τοῖς παρὰ σοῦ μεταλημφομέ-
 νοις τῶν προκειμένων ὑπαρχόντων καὶ οἰκοπέδων, καὶ
 χρᾶσθαι καὶ διοικεῖν περὶ αὐτῶν ὡς ἐὰν αἰρή, καὶ ἐξουσίαν ἔχειν εἰ
 ἑτέροις π[ω]λεῖν, ἅπερ ἐπάναγκες παρέξομαί σοι βέβαια διὰ παν-
 20 τὸς ἀπὸ πάντων πάσῃ βεβαιώσει, καὶ καθαρὰ ἀπὸ τε γεωργίας βασιλει-
 κῆς καὶ οὐσιακῆς γῆς καὶ παντὸς εἴδους καὶ ἀπ[ὸ] φειλῆς καὶ κατο-
 χῆς πάσης [δ]ημοσίας τε καὶ ιδιωτικῆς, καὶ τὰ μὲν σειτικά καὶ ἀμπε-
 λικά ἐδ[άφ]η ἀπὸ ἀπεργασίας καὶ ὑδροφυλακίας χωμάτων, ἔτι δὲ καὶ
 ἀπὸ τῶν ὑπὲρ αὐτῶν τελουμένων δημοσίων τ[ε]λεσμάτων καὶ ἐπι-
 κλασμῶν κα[ὶ] ἐπιμερισμῶν παντοίων τῶν ἕως ἐπαγομένων κ[αὶ] αὐ-
 25 τῶν ἐπαγ[ο]μένων τοῦ ἐνεστῶτος α (ἔτους) διὰ τὸ τὰ ἀπ[ὸ] τοῦ εἰσιόν[τ]ος β (ἔτους) τῶν
 τῶν πρό[σ]φωρα εἶναι σοῦ τοῦ ὠνουμένου, πρὸς ὅ[ν] καὶ εἶν[αι] τὰ ἀπὸ τοῦ αὐ-
 τοῦ εἰσιόν[τ]ος β (ἔτους) τελέσματα παντοῖ[α], τῶν δὲ ἐπελ[ευσόμ]ενον
 ἢ ἐμποιη[σ]όμενον ἀποστήσειν παραχρῆμα τοῖς ἰδίοις ἀ[ν]ηλώμασι
 καθάπ[ε]ρ ἐκ δίκης. κυρία ἢ πρᾶσις τρισσῆ γραφεῖσα, [ἦ]νπερ ὀπηνικά
 25 ἐὰν αἰρή δημοσιώσεις διὰ τοῦ καταλογίου, οὐ προσδε[όμενος μετα-]

[λήμψεως μου οὐδὲ ἐτ[έρας μου εὐδο]κήσεως δι[ιὰ τὸ ἐντεῦθεν]
lines missing

5 ὑπὲρ: ὑπερ 10 ἐγγόνοις: ἐγγονοῖς 11 ὑπαρχόντων: ὑπ-
 13 ἐπάναγκες: -αναγ'κες 16 ἰδιωτικῆς: ἰδ- 17 ὑδροφυλακίας: ὑδρο- 22 ἰδίοις: ἰδ-

Translation (Gainsford):

... in the village of Seryphis ... and a complete pigeon-house, and a house, and a courtyard with furniture and all related goods, all of which is neighbouring Tasot[a(?)] to the south, a canal to the north, a public street to the east, and other bare spaces to the west. ⁵ The payment agreed between each of us for all of the aforementioned properties, of 12,000 drachmas, silver and of the mint of Augustus, which is two talents of silver, I received in full on the spot; in *stipulatio* I agreed that it was counted from your hand in full. So (I agreed) that you, ¹⁰ with your descendents and successors, possess and own the aforementioned properties and buildings, and that you have the right to use them and administer their affairs however you choose, and if (you wish) to sell them to others; and I shall be required to provide them to you secure for all time, against all claims, with every guarantee, and free of royal farmland, ¹⁵ estate land, any habitation, and any debt or hindrance either public or private; and the taxable grain and vine lands (free) of soil upkeep and irrigation (debts); and furthermore (free) of public property taxes for them, damage, and division of any kind, up until the intercalary days and ²⁰ during the intercalary days themselves of the current (year) 1, because from the beginning of (year) 2 the profits from the property are yours, having bought it; so also, from the beginning of (year) 2, are taxes of all kinds, and the one who succeeds or takes over will at once give up (any claim) for personal costs, just as if from a lawsuit. The governing contract is written in triplicate, and at any time ²⁵ you choose you may publish it through the register, without needing my participation or other approval from me, since from then ...

6. Te Papa GH023790.
Wine delivery order

Dimensions: 74 mm (H) × 103 mm (W)

Date: 5th-6th century CE?

Gift of the Egypt Exploration Fund to the Wellington Dominion Museum, 1913; transferred to Te Papa Tongarewa, 1992.

Notes (PG):

Unpublished. The correspondence with the Egypt Exploration Fund at the time of acquisition, in late 1912, tends to suggest that Oxyrhynchus is the most likely provenance, but that cannot be certain.

Most of the transcription below is based on suggestions made by W. Graham Claytor (Hunter College, CUNY) and T. M. Hickey (Berkeley) via social media, for which we are very grateful.

We have the top and right margins, but no greeting or heading. The dashed lines at the left indicate a list. Lines 1 and 3 κνίδ(ια) ‘Knidian (jars of wine)’ is a standard measure. The abbreviation / for -ια is not listed in McNamee’s catalogue of abbreviations (*Abbreviations in Greek literary papyri and ostraca*, Ann Arbor: Scholars Press, 1981). πρωτόληνα, written in line 2 as προτόλ(ηνα), also appears with προτο- in [P. Lond. 5 1881](#) (= [P. Brit. Lib. 1638 a](#), 6th-8th cent.), line 7 (πρωτόλημα).

References:

Te Papa: <http://collections.tepapa.govt.nz/object/1347931>

Text, recto (diplomatic):

- 1 [] .. []κνιδ/ρλ
 2 []μ προτῶλ .
 3 []μ . . . οινῶκνιδ/ ἰ
 4 [] . ομλαγ .
 5 [] . []πῆρ .

Text, recto:

- 1 [] .. []κνίδ(ια) ρλ
 2 []μ προτῶλ(ηνα) .
 3 []μ . . . οἴνο(υ) κνίδ(ια) ἰ
 4 [] . ὀμ(οίως) λάγ(υνοι)
 5 [] . [ὕ]πῆρ .

Translation (Gainsford):

- ... jars, 130(?) ...
 ... wine from first vat
 ... jars of wine, 10
 ... same number of flasks
⁵ ... on behalf of ...